

**AN ANALYSIS ON THE AWARENESS AND PRACTICES OF CONSUMER PROTECTION RIGHTS UNDER
REPUBLIC ACT NO. 7394 AMONG STUDENTS OF ISU-CAUAYAN CITY CAMPUS**

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ABSTRACT

In the Philippines, Republic Act No. 7394, known as the Consumer Act of 1992, stands as landmark legislation aimed at protecting and promoting the rights and responsibilities of consumers. This study determines the level of awareness of students from Isabela State University-Cauayan City Campus regarding their consumer rights, the prevalence of practicing their consumer responsibilities, the sources that influenced their awareness of the law, and whether there is a significant difference in awareness when grouped according to their enrolled programs. To gather information relevant to the topic, the researchers employed a quantitative approach, using self-administered questionnaires via Google Forms. The data were treated, tabulated, and analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, means, and ANOVA. The findings show that respondents were 'moderately aware' of the provisions protecting their consumer rights and practiced their rights 'often' in traditional transactions. Generally, respondents understood the aspects of the law that protect their rights and responsibilities. Social media sites such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter were the most common information sources on the topic. It was also found that there is a significant difference in awareness levels when respondents were grouped according to their enrolled programs. The BS Legal Management Program showed the highest level of awareness compared to other groups. The observed difference in awareness levels and the associated statistical significance (as indicated by the mean difference and p-value) could be attributed to factors such as the extensive inclusion of business and law-related subjects in management-related programs. Therefore, management students receive more in-depth discussions and exposure to legal concepts, leading to higher awareness levels. Based on these findings, it is recommended that universities conduct informative conferences on relevant laws, such as the Consumer Rights of the Philippines of 1992, which protect consumers against health and safety hazards, as well as deceptive, unfair, and unconscionable sales acts and practices. Additionally, further studies can explore the relationship between respondents' demographic profiles, such as income, educational attainment, and geographic location, and their awareness, knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions regarding their consumer rights and responsibilities.

Keywords: *consumer, consumer protection rights, consumer responsibilities, traditional transactions*

INTRODUCTION

In developing nations like the Philippines, consumer rights awareness remains a significant concern amid instances where these rights are often overlooked or taken for granted (Ibarra & Revilla, 2014). Despite increasing local efforts to prioritize consumer welfare, data regarding public awareness of fundamental consumer rights are scarce. Republic Act No. 7394, or the Consumer Act of the Philippines, is a pivotal legislation aimed at safeguarding consumer rights by ensuring transparency, choice, and recourse for grievances (Republic Act No. 7394, 1992).

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This legal framework delineates consumer entitlements and specifies corresponding responsibilities, fostering fair trade practices, product safety, and avenues for conflict resolution (Ibarra & Revilla, 2014).

The Consumer Act of the Philippines enshrines fundamental rights and responsibilities of consumers, encompassing aspects such as the right to information, the right to choose, and the right to redress grievances, among others. This legal framework not only articulates the entitlements of consumers but also delineates the corresponding responsibilities accompanying these rights. The Act, enacted to protect and promote the welfare of consumers, is a critical instrument in fostering fair trade practices, ensuring product quality and safety, and providing mechanisms for dispute resolution (The Consumer Act of the Philippines, Republic Act No. 7394, April 19, 1992). The National Consumer Affairs Council (NCAC) was created by this law and composed of government, consumer organizations, and business sector representatives to improve consumer programs' management, coordination, and efficacy (Ibarra & Revilla, 2014).

According to Nedumaran and Mehala (2019), consumer awareness encompasses understanding various redress mechanisms, consumer protection laws, and specific rights such as safety, health protection, and product quality and pricing information. Such awareness is crucial in protecting consumers from exploitation within the complexities of the global economy (Ingawale et al., 2018). Under Chapter V, Article 97 of Republic Act No. 7394, commonly known as the Consumer Act of the Philippines, stringent provisions are in place to hold accountable manufacturers, producers, and importers for any damages resulting from defects in their products, regardless of fault (Catriz et al., 2022). This legal stipulation underscores the legislative commitment to protect consumers by imposing strict liability on entities responsible for defective products, ensuring that consumers have recourse for damages caused by issues ranging from design flaws to inadequate product information.

Legal precedents further illustrate the application and enforcement of these consumer protections. In the case of *Aowa Electronic Philippines, Inc. v. Department of Trade & Industry- NCR*, the court addressed allegations of deceptive sales practices, where consumers were misled into believing they had won gifts contingent upon additional purchases, highlighting violations under Articles 50 and 52 of the Consumer Act. Such cases not only reinforce the legal framework's intent to safeguard consumer rights but also serve as deterrents against unfair trade practices.

Similarly, the case of *Autozentrum Alabang Inc. v. Spouses Bernardo* exemplifies the Consumer Act's role in protecting consumers from misrepresentation and in this instance, misrepresenting a certified pre-owned car as new led to legal repercussions under Section 50 of RA 7394, highlighting the Act's provisions aimed at preventing deceptive sales practices and ensuring consumer confidence (*Autozentrum Alabang, Inc. v. Spouses Bernardo*, 786 Phil. 851, June 08, 2016, Carpio, J.). These legal precedents underscore the importance of robust consumer protection legislation like the Consumer Act of the Philippines in safeguarding consumer interests and promoting fair trade practices. By holding businesses accountable for product defects and deceptive practices, the law protects individual consumers and fosters a marketplace based on transparency, fairness, and consumer trust.

Consumers' best defense lies in their thorough understanding of their rights and responsibilities. They must be prepared to assert these rights actively in the marketplace to ensure fair treatment and equitable outcomes in all transactions. Simultaneously, consumers are responsible for acquiring, evaluating, and utilizing available information about products and services. This informed approach empowers them to make prudent purchasing decisions that align with their needs and preferences (Ibarra & Revilla, 2014).

In developing nations such as the Philippines, where issues of neglect and disregard for consumer rights persist, assessing the level of awareness among Filipinos regarding their rights poses significant challenges. Despite growing local efforts to emphasize consumer welfare, data on public perceptions of these foundational rights remains scarce. The Consumer Act of the Philippines explicitly outlines consumers' fundamental rights and obligations; however, its effectiveness in enhancing awareness among the Filipino population remains uncertain.

A notable research gap exists concerning the extent of awareness among Filipino consumers, particularly students, regarding their rights as stipulated in the Consumer Act of 1992. Despite legislative efforts and increasing emphasis on consumer protection in the Philippines, there is limited empirical evidence on the actual awareness

levels among the population, especially among students actively engaged in commercial activities. Current literature lacks comprehensive studies that systematically assess consumer rights' awareness, understanding, and practical application among diverse demographic groups, including students from various academic disciplines. Addressing this gap is crucial for informing targeted consumer education initiatives and policy enhancements to bolster consumer protection frameworks in the Philippines. Therefore, this study determined the level of awareness among students regarding their consumer protection rights as outlined in the Consumer Act of 1992, identify the sources of information that influenced their awareness, assess the frequency with which they practice their consumer protection rights in traditional transactions, and examine whether there is a significant difference in the level of awareness among respondents when grouped according to their degree programs.

METHODS

This study employed a quantitative approach to evaluate respondents' awareness of consumer protection rights under the Consumer Act of 1992. It was conducted at Isabela State University- Cauayan City Campus, San Fermin, Cauayan City, Isabela. The participants included thirty (30) B.S. Legal Management students from the School of Arts and Sciences (SAS) who had studied the Retail Trade Law and Consumer Act with E-Commerce subjects and other students who had not, namely twenty-seven (27) B.S. Business Administration students from the College of Business and Management, twenty-seven (27) B.S. Industrial Technology Major in Automotive, twenty-six (26) B.S. Industrial Technology Major in Electronics from the Polytechnic School, twenty-six (26) B.S. Information Technology Major in Web Mobile Application Development students from the College of Computing Studies, Information and Communication Technologies (CCSICT), and twenty-six (26) B.S. in Education Major in Science students from the College of Education of ISU-Cauayan City Campus. A total of 162 respondents participated in the study.

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents as to Program Enrolled

Program Enrolled	Frequency	Percentage
BS Business Administration	27	16.7%
B.S. Industrial Technology (Automotive)	27	16.7%
B.S. Industrial Technology (Electronics)	26	16%
B.S. Legal Management	30	18.5%
B.S. Information Technology (Web & Mobile Application Development)	26	16%
B.S. Education (Science)	26	16%

*Note: Total may not equal 100% due to rounding errors.

Convenience sampling was utilized to gather data, and a self-administered questionnaire was developed using Google Forms, which underwent validation by a legal expert in consumer protection law. Data collection occurred from March to April 2024, facilitated by instructors coordinating with class representatives for survey distribution. The questionnaire consisted of four sections: Section I covered demographic information such as age, gender, and program enrolled; Section II included eleven questions measured on a 4-point Likert scale to assess awareness of consumer protection rights; Section III queried sources of information on consumer rights; and Section IV explored the frequency of practicing consumer rights in traditional transactions.

To assess the questionnaire's reliability, the researchers conducted a pilot test with thirty (30) A.B. Political Science students from the School of Arts and Sciences (SAS). Internal consistency was evaluated using Cronbach's Alpha, which measures how closely related a set of items are as a group, indicating scale reliability. It is important to note that a high Alpha value does not necessarily indicate unidimensionality (Bruin, 2006). Sections II and IV of the questionnaire yielded an alpha value of 0.894 and 0.834, respectively, which implies good internal consistency. Likewise, content validity was also determined through a review by an expert on RA 7394.

Additionally, content validity was ensured through expert review referencing RA 7394. Data analysis involved using descriptive and inferential statistics, i.e., ANOVA.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Awareness Among Students regarding their Consumer Protection Rights as Outlined in the Consumer Act of 1992

The respondents were found to be *'moderately aware'* of the provisions that protect their consumer rights. Statement no. 9, which claims a refund from the manufacturer, distributor, or seller for the purchase price if the product turns out to be damaged, harmful, or unsafe, gained the highest mean, 2.92, with a qualitative description of "Moderately Aware." It is followed by statements no. 4 and 6, which both earned the same mean of 2.88, and which are about seeking help from the Department of Health (DOH) concerning food, drugs, cosmetics, devices, and substances that caused harm to the health and safety of the consumer, and seeking help from the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) concerning consumer products which emerged from deceptive, unfair, and unethical sales acts and practices, respectively. Both these statements suggest a consistent level of awareness on the topic. This indicates that the respondents, on average, strongly agreed or were moderately aware of their right to redress and seek help from appropriate government agencies for such cases. However, there may still be room for improvement, as shown by the qualitative description of 'Moderately Aware' for the statements with the highest means.

Table 2. Item Mean Distribution on the Level of Awareness of the Respondents on their Consumer Rights as provided for in Republic Act No. 7394

No.	Questions/Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Scale
1	Any product that I buy, the manufacturers (both foreign and domestic), producers, and importers shall be liable for it if damaged.	2.86	0.792	Moderately Aware
2	Under R.A. 7394, consumers are protected against unfair/illegal sales acts and practices	2.80	0.818	Moderately Aware
3	Under R.A. 7394, consumers are protected against unethical/unlawful sales acts and practices	2.78	0.890	Moderately Aware
4	I can report and seek help from the Department of Health (DOH) concerning food, drugs, cosmetics, devices, and substances I have bought that have caused harm to my health and safety as a consumer.	2.88	0.814	Moderately Aware
5	I can report and seek help from the Department of Agriculture (DA) concerning the products related to agriculture that I have bought which caused harm to my health and safety as a consumer and which emerged from deceptive, unfair, and unethical sales acts and practices.	2.83	0.806	Moderately Aware
6	I can report and seek help from the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) concerning consumer products I have bought, which emerged from deceptive, unfair, and unethical sales acts and practices.	2.88	0.754	Moderately Aware
7	I can petition the appropriate government agency about the products bought from the manufacturer, distributor, or seller that are considered damaged, injurious, and unsafe.	2.82	0.771	Moderately Aware
8	The appropriate government agency can direct the manufacturer, distributor, or seller to replace the damaged product with a like or equivalent product that complies with the applicable consumer product standards and does not contain damages.	2.84	0.739	Moderately Aware

9	If I bought products that are damaged, injurious, and unsafe, I have a right to claim a refund from the manufacturer, distributor, or seller for the product's purchase price.	2.92	0.811	Moderately Aware
10	The appropriate government agency can direct the manufacturer, distributor, or seller to pay me for reasonable damages if the department determines that the products I have bought are damaged, injurious, and unsafe.	2.86	0.808	Moderately Aware
11	Under R.A. 7394, if any product I buy is damaged, the manufacturers (both foreign and domestic), producers, and importers shall be liable for it.	2.84	0.780	Moderately Aware
Overall Awareness		2.85	0.65	Moderately Aware

On the other hand, the statement which gained the lowest mean, 2.78, is statement no. 3, which states that under R.A 7394, as a consumer, one is protected against unethical/unlawful sales acts and practices; this is followed by statement no. 2, which states that under R.A 7394, as a consumer, one is protected against unfair/illegal sales acts and practices, with a mean of 2.80. This indicates a lower level of awareness regarding their right to safety.

The overall mean is 2.85, which manifests that the respondents are "Moderately Aware" of their consumer protection rights. While respondents demonstrate a comparatively lower awareness of their right to safety, their awareness of rights concerning redress mechanisms and avenues for seeking help is still strong. This discrepancy in awareness levels implies a potential gap in education or information dissemination regarding comprehensive consumer rights.

This finding is supported by the study conducted by Sun (2018), stating that, at present, the legal awareness and legal knowledge of college students generally show a stable and healthy condition. Most students can abide by the law, regard the law as the code of conduct, and protect themselves with the law (Ma, 2018). Likewise, Chhetri (2020) stated that college students' knowledge level on consumerism is quite good. His study noted that their practices and behavior during the buying process are appreciable.

Sources of Information Which Influenced Respondents' Awareness of their Consumer Protection Rights

The most surfaced source of all the information sources listed is social media platforms (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, etc.). This shows that many respondents rely on social media platforms to obtain information about R.A. 7394. Social media's popularity as an information source is likely due to its widespread accessibility and the ease with which information can be shared and disseminated across various social networks. It can be a means of helping digital citizens reclaim their rights as well as a tool for helping them understand their options as consumers in today's society. Nowadays, the internet can push and promote awareness at a fast global pace. Some consumer education campaigns have successfully used social media for wider audiences.

Table 3. Frequency and Percentage Distribution as to Information Sources regarding Republic Act No. 7394

Information Sources	Frequency	Percentage
Television (Shows, Advertisements)	54	33%
Printed Materials (Newspapers, Magazines, Posters, Brochures, etc.)	26	16%
Radio Programs	20	12.3%
Government Websites (dti.gov.ph., doh.go.ph., da.gov.ph.)	37	22.8%
Social Media Platforms (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, etc.)	113	69.8%
Others	41	25.3%

On the other hand, radio programs emerged as the least chosen medium for obtaining information about R.A. 7394, which could be attributed to some factors, such as its declining popularity and the accessibility of radio programs depending on the consumers' geographical location, socio-economic status, which could potentially limit its reach, as compared to social media platforms.

Prevalence of Practicing their Consumer Protection Rights in Traditional Transactions

The respondents were provided seven (7) statements to assess whether they always, often, sometimes, or never practice their consumer protection rights. The findings show that the respondents often practice their consumer rights in traditional transactions. Six (6) practices were "often" practiced, and one (1) was always practiced and observed. Statement no. 7, which involves checking the quality of the product before buying it, gained the highest mean score of 3.02 (Sd=0.895) and was described as "always" practiced. This shows that respondents consistently prioritize checking the quality of products before making a purchase, indicating a strong commitment to ensuring that they receive value for their money and avoid purchasing faulty or substandard goods. Likewise, statement no. 6, which pertains to checking the labels of each product before buying it, received a mean score of 3.16 (Sd=0.870) and was described as "often" practiced. This indicates that while respondents may not always check product labels before purchasing, they do so frequently enough to be considered a common practice. This behavior demonstrates critical awareness among consumers regarding product information and ingredients. Both manifest a dynamic approach to consumerism and highlight the importance of informed decision-making and critical awareness in the marketplace.

Table 4. Item Mean Distribution as to the Practices Regarding Consumer Protection Rights in Traditional Transactions

No.	Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Scale
1	I ask for receipts after purchasing products or availing services.	2.90	0.943	Often
2	I scan if a product has no damage before purchasing it.	3.14	0.884	Often
3	I buy food products from known supermarkets such as Save More, Pure Gold, Robinson's, etc.	2.88	0.854	Often
4	I look for products which are approved by the FDA or DTI.	3.02	0.895	Often
5	I check a product's reviews before purchasing it.	3.17	0.853	Often
6	I check the labels of each product before purchasing it.	3.16	0.870	Often
7	I check the quality of the product before buying it.	3.34	0.741	Always
Overall		3.09	0.67	Often

On the other hand, two statements gained the lowest mean score. Statement no. 3, which pertains to buying food products from known supermarkets, received a low mean score of 2.88 (Sd=0.854), indicating a potential lack of emphasis on food safety, quality assurance, or trust in known brands or establishments. Likewise, statement no. 1, which involves asking for receipts after purchasing products or availing services, indicates that they do not consistently practice obtaining receipts, as it is a crucial consumer practice that also serves as proof of purchase and can be necessary for warranty claims, returns, or resolving disputes.

Observed Difference in Awareness Levels when Grouped as to Program Enrolled and its' Statistical Significance

Regarding group descriptives, BSIT-Automotive has 27 respondents with a mean of 3.2 (Sd=0.597). Respondents from B.S. Legal Management got the second-highest mean, 3.18 (Sd =0.532). B.S. Education (General Science) has 26 respondents with a mean of 2.86 (Sd = 0.67), followed by BSIT-Electronics with 26 respondents with

a mean of 2.83 (Sd = 0.58). BSIT-WMAD has 26 respondents with a mean of 2.48 (Sd= 0.611). Lastly, BS Business Administration has 27 respondents with a mean of 2.47 (Sd= 0.525).

Table 5. Group Descriptive on the Level of Awareness on Consumer Protection Rights

Program Enrolled	N	Mean	SD	F	df	P
BS Industrial Technology (Automotive)	27	3.2	0.597	8.13	5,156	<.001
B.S. Industrial Technology (Electronics)	26	2.83	0.58			
BS Information Technology (WMAD)	26	2.48	0.611			
BS Legal Management	30	3.18	0.532			
BS Education (General Science)	26	2.86	0.67			
BS Business Administration	27	2.47	0.525			

The p-value measures the strength of evidence against the null hypothesis. A p-value less than .001 indicates strong evidence against the null hypothesis. As a result, the alternative hypothesis that claims a significant difference between the respondents' level of awareness when grouped according to their program enrollment was accepted, as the p-value is less than <.001. This shows a significant difference in the level of awareness when the respondents are grouped according to their program enrolled, as seen in the mean difference and p-value of BSLM, a management-related program, manifesting a high level of awareness as to the topic.

The observed difference in awareness levels and the associated statistical significance (as indicated by the mean difference and p-value) could be attributed to several factors. First, management-related programs such as B.S. Legal Management extensively include subjects related to businesses and laws, compared to non-management programs. Therefore, management students receive more in-depth discussions and exposure to legal concepts, leading to higher awareness levels. Likewise, management students with career aspirations in the legal field, where understanding this topic is necessary, continuously seek information and resources on consumer protection laws.

According to a study conducted by Catriz et al. (2022), the cause as to why management students are likely to have high awareness of the law may be because it is natural for them to tackle laws that discuss people's rights, security, and protection. Thus, there is a significant difference in the respondents' awareness of the programs they are enrolled in. Likewise, a study conducted by Rawal in 2021 indicated that management students' awareness level is higher than non-management programs. This is backed by a study by Fitzgerald (1997) entitled Student Awareness of Consumer Rights and Services at Oklahoma State University, which determined that students' awareness varied according to their chosen programs. Likewise,

In a study conducted by Ma (2018), it was found that in colleges and universities, the cultivation of college students' legal awareness should respond to the call of the new era and guide the students to meet the era's requirements so that students can take the rule of law as one of their ideological weapons. Therefore, it is required that colleges and universities strengthen legal education and educate students comprehensively to cultivate qualified builders for the new era of socialism. The study also recommended increasing elective courses for basic legal knowledge. Elective law courses can be appropriately set up to enhance students' basic legal knowledge, including the Constitution, the Criminal Law, the Civil Law, and the Commercial Law. These basic elective courses allow students to understand the fundamental theories of jurisprudence and lay the foundation for the subsequent courses combining their major courses and laws.

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers conclude that students from the Isabela State University-Cauayan City Campus are 'moderately aware' of the provisions that protect their consumer rights and practice their rights 'often' in traditional transactions, as provided for in Republic Act No. 7394, otherwise known as the Consumer Act of the Philippines of 1992. This means that the respondents can understand the aspects of the law that protect their rights as consumers. It was also found that Social Media Platforms (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter) are the

information sources that influenced the respondents' awareness of their rights as consumers. Using the One-Way ANOVA, the researchers learned that at least one of the means is different, and there is a significant difference when the respondents are grouped according to the program they are enrolled in. B.S. Legal Management manifested the highest level of awareness about the topic compared to the other pre-existing group. The observed difference in awareness levels and the associated statistical significance (as indicated by the mean difference and p-value) could be attributed to several factors, one being as a management-related program, including subjects related to businesses and laws extensively, compared to non-management programs. Therefore, management students receive more in-depth discussions and exposure to legal concepts, leading to higher awareness levels. Likewise, management students with career aspirations in the legal field, where understanding this topic is necessary, continuously seek out information and resources on consumer protection laws.

The results of the study underscore the potential benefits of universities organizing informative sessions focused on relevant laws, such as those safeguarding consumer rights in the Philippines. These sessions could enhance understanding among students from various disciplines, promoting broader awareness and application of consumer protection laws. Additionally, future research could explore how demographic factors such as income, educational attainment, and geographic location influence awareness, knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions regarding consumer rights and responsibilities, providing further insights into effective educational strategies and policy interventions.

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